

The Genebank Academy: Building global capacity in crop conservation

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SUMMARY

Learners interested in gaining knowledge in genebank management and crop conservation practices often do not know where to start looking online. BOLD addresses this challenge with the Genebank Academy, a centralized online platform that consolidates and creates high quality training materials from partner organizations, including the Crop Trust. This represents an important milestone in how training for genebank management is organized and offered. In addition to curating existing courses, BOLD is also developing new, targeted training to support project implementation among partners. The Genebank Academy hosts materials covering aspects of *ex situ* conservation, from fundamental genebank principles to data systems, from conservation strategies to regulatory compliance. The platform offers flexible learning opportunities for both beginners and professionals working in crop diversity conservation, to strengthen their skills and better support their work and studies. With the launch of the Genebank Academy, key training materials on genebank management and plant genetic resources are brought together on a single, curated platform, reducing the time and effort required for learners to find trusted content.

NO CENTRALIZED TRAINING PLATFORM

Flexible learning materials are created and offered by many institutions including the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the CGIAR, Colorado State University and many others. While many of these institutions offer high quality, free or low-cost online courses, none focus specifically on genebanks.

Learners often need to conduct extensive online searches across multiple platforms to gain a complete understanding of genebank management and operations. Small differences in search terms may lead to missing important training resources, resulting in time-consuming and fragmented learning. BOLD has removed this barrier by providing a centralized hub that ensures learners and BOLD partners have access to comprehensive, organized training materials without the burden of navigating multiple platforms.

BOLD gathered knowledge from partner institutions and develop its own courses. BOLD pooled leading experts in these topics, ensuring each partner acquires a common understanding of these principles for effective crop conservation.

GENEBANK ACADEMY AS THE SOLUTION

The Genebank Academy was developed in 2025 under the BOLD's capacity and resources development initiative. The Genebank Academy team curated existing courses from partner institutions, covering topics ranging from genebank quality management to policy related to plant genetic resources conservation and management. These courses are systematically organized on the platform, allowing learners to easily filter content by topic and organization. Most courses are short, can be completed within a few hours and offer certificates upon completion. Learners can include these certificates in their CVs or LinkedIn profiles to demonstrate ongoing professional development and new skills.

In parallel, the team has also developed several structured, step-by-step online courses designed to support BOLD and other Crop Trust partners with project implemen-

tation, such as reporting, risk management, financial management and compliance, to help partners improve the way they meet their obligations as part of their partnership and to support more efficient, transparent project delivery. The Genebank Academy team continues to maintain and update the training materials to align with changes in project implementation.

BUILDING THE GENE BANK ACADEMY FOR THE FUTURE

Within the Genebank Academy, learners can progress at their own pace and apply their knowledge from the academy to research, operations, or policy work. Future steps of the academy include creating new courses, mapping additional training resources worldwide, expanding collaborations and host more partner-developed materials on the platform and building formal recognition or certification for Genebank Academy courses.

BOLD envisions the Genebank Academy as an open learning space and centralized source of practical, high-quality information that strengthens global awareness, knowledge, and skills in genebank management and operations, thereby helping to ensure that crop diversity is conserved and remains available for use globally, now and in the future.

Visit the Genebank Academy at <https://www.croptrust.org/knowledge-hub/genebank-academy/>

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